

Synthesis of *N*-Glucopyranosyl Benzothiazolyl Thiocarbamides

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1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-substituted-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides (3) have been prepared by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate and 2-aminobenzothiazole/substituted-benzothiazoles.

RECENTLY, we have reported several *N*-glucosyl thiocarbamides involving interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate with ammonia and aryl/alkyl amines^{1,2}. In the present communication the synthesis of a few 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-substituted-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides (3) have been reported.

The reaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1) and 2-aminobenzothiazole (2a) in boiling dry benzene afforded a clear solution. On removing benzene a syrupy mass was left, which on repeated trituration with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) followed by treatment with ethanol gave a white granular solid (3a). On crystallisation from ethanol pure (3a) was obtained, m.p. 166°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 43.47^\circ$ (c 1.564 in CHCl₃). Its ir spectrum clearly indicated the presence of NH (3180), C=O (1735), C=N (1585), C=S (1220), C-S (750 cm⁻¹) and band at 900 cm⁻¹ due to β -D-glucopyranosyl ring deformation³⁻⁵. Its nmr spectrum displayed signals⁶ due to acetyl protons at δ 2.02 and aromatic protons at 7.8-7.2. Signals in the form of multiplets characteristic of the pyranosyl ring protons⁷ were also located at δ 4.1-5.2. In its mass spectrum^{8,9} the molecular ion peak at *m/e* 539 was located along with other fragment peaks. Probable fragmentation pattern along with *m/e* are shown in Scheme 1.

3a was desulphurisable with boiling alkaline plumbite solution. On reaction with benzyl chloride in boiling ethanol followed by treatment with dilute ammonium hydroxide, 3a formed a *S*-benzyl derivative, 4a (as a free base), m.p. 172°; $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 60.15^\circ$ (c 0.263 in CHCl₃). These facts confirm the assigned structure of 3a, m.p. 166°.

The reaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate was also extended to several other substituted-benzothiazoles and the corresponding products (3b-g) were isolated (Table 1).

Attempts have also been made towards the deacetylation of 3 using methanolic ammonia, but without success.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

where, a R=H, b R=4-Me, c R=5-Me, d R=6-Me,
e R=4-Cl, f R=5-Cl, g R=6-Cl;
Ac=Acetyl, Bz=Benzyl

TABLE 1—1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-substituted-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides (3).
Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate used, 0.02 *M*, 7.7 g. Solvent : Benzene

Sl. no.	Substituted-benzothiazoles (2), g	1-Tetra- <i>O</i> -acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-substituted-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides (3), g	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		[α] _D ²⁰ in CHCl ₃
				N	S	
1.	2-Amino (a), 3	3-(2)-benzothiazolyl (a), 4.2	166	7.71 (7.79)	11.60 (11.87)	-48.47° (c 1.564)
2.	2-Amino-(4-methyl) (b), 3.2	3-(2)-4-methyl (b) 5	206	7.38 (7.59)	11.29 (11.57)	-64.39° (c 1.533)
3.	2-Amino (5-methyl) (c), 3.2	3-(2)-5 methyl (c), 4.9	196	7.68 (7.59)	11.48 (11.57)	-56.91° (c 0.606)
4.	2-Amino-(6-methyl) (d), 3.2	3-(2)-6-methyl (d), 5.2	194	7.66 (7.59)	12.16 (11.57)	-44.27° (c 1.598)
5.	2-Amino-(4-chloro) (e), 3.6	3-(2)-4-chloro (e), 4.8	180	6.91 (7.32)	10.86 (11.15)	-28.84° (c 1.357)
6.	2-Amino-(5-chloro) (f), 3.6	3-(2)-5-chloro (f), 5.4	199	7.89 (7.32)	10.92 (11.15)	-39.63° (c 1.501)
7.	2-Amino-(6-chloro) (g), 3.6	3-(2)-6-chloro (g), 5.2	158	7.26 (7.32)	10.98 (11.15)	-43.19° (c 0.606)

Experimental

The required tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate and 2-aminobenzothiazole/substituted benzothiazoles were prepared by the methods described earlier^{1,2,10,11}.

1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-(2)-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide (3a): The benzene solution of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl isothiocyanate (0.02 *M*, 7.7 g in 40 ml) was mixed with a suspension of 2-aminobenzothiazole (0.02 *M*, 3 g in 20 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed over a steam bath for 4 h. Benzene was then removed by distillation and the resultant syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). Finally, it was treated with ethanol when a white solid (4.2 g) was obtained, which was crystallised from ethanol to yield pure 3a, m.p. 166° (Found : N, 7.71 ; S, 11.60. C₂₂H₂₅O₉N₃S₂ requires N, 7.79 ; S, 11.87%).

S-Benzyl-1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-(2)-benzothiazolyl isothiocarbamide (4a): A mixture of 1-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-glucopyranosyl-3-(2)-benzothiazolyl thiocarbamide (0.01 *M*, 5.3 g), benzyl chloride (0.01 *M*, 1.2 g) and ethanol (25 ml) was heated under gentle reflux for 90 min. The resultant acidic solution was cooled and rendered basic with dilute ammonium hydroxide when a sticky mass was obtained, which on treatment with ethanol was converted to a granular solid 4a (3.5 g), crystallised

from ethanol, m.p. 172° (Found : N, 6.52. C₂₉H₃₁O₉N₃S₂ requires N, 6.67%).

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